

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D3.3 - Platform available for all stakeholders (Version 2)

Authors:

Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)

August 2023 (M24) - WP3, D3.3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450. The views expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author/s and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Technical References

Project Acronym	ePLANET
Project Title	European Local Public Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition

Deliverable No.	D3.3
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP3 - Digitalisation
Lead beneficiary	01 (CIMNE)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	06 (DDGI), 07 (RDFC), 08 (EAZK)
Due date of deliverable	31 th August 2023
Actual submission date	21 th August 2023

Authors	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
Contributors	Josep MAYOS (CIMNE), Xavier PALOMÉ (DDGI), Maite SELLART (CIMNE), Marcelo LAMPKOWSKI (ICLEI EURO)

Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
1.0	9/09/22	Table of content and structure	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
1.1	27/09/22	First draft	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE), Francesc CONTRERAS (CIMNE)
1.2	4/10/22	Full draft	Josep MAYOS (CIMNE) Francesc CONTRERAS (CIMNE)
1.3	10/10/22	Peer-review	Xavier PALOMÉ (DDGI)
1.4	10/10/22	Final version	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
2.0	30/05/23	Table of content and structure	Josep MAYOS (CIMNE)
2.1	10/08/23	First draft	Maite SELLART (CIMNE) Josep MAYOS (CIMNE) Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
2.2	14/08/23	Peer-review	Marcelo LAMPKOWSKI (ICLEI EURO)
2.3	17/08/23	Final version	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)

Table of content

1	Introduction	9
2	ePLANET federated platform	10
2.1	Preliminary concepts.....	12
2.2	UC1 - Digitalisation of SECAPs drafting and monitoring process	14
2.3	UC2 - Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock	23
2.4	UC3 - GEO-Tools for the promotion of energy communities	27
2.4.1	<i>Crete island pilot</i>	<i>27</i>
2.4.2	<i>Girona province pilot</i>	<i>28</i>
2.4.2.1	<i>Study of energy community's creation existing platforms</i>	<i>28</i>
2.4.2.2	<i>Energy community's creation platforms development</i>	<i>29</i>
2.5	UC4 - PV potential analysis for public buildings.....	31
3	Platform continuous engagement and improvements	32
3.1	Platform training.....	32
3.2	Usability test survey results and conclusions	33
3.2.1	<i>The platform usability in Girona pilot</i>	<i>36</i>
3.2.2	<i>The platform usability in Crete pilot</i>	<i>36</i>
3.2.3	<i>The platform usability in the Zlín region pilot</i>	<i>37</i>
4	Conclusions	38
	Annex 1 Energy Communities promotion platforms state of the art.....	39
	Annex 2 Usability testing survey	44

Executive Summary

The ePLANET platform consists of different services that covers the needs and wishes identified in the surveys performed in the pilot sites and that are set as use cases. This set of services will be implemented through different tools and applications that will constitute the ePLANET federated platform, a multi-platform adapted to the pilot sites and easily scalable to other regions within the EU.

This document is the second version of three that will be presented at the end of each year with the status and developments of the platform end-user interfaces.

List of Figures

Figure 2-1 The ePLANET federated platform	10
Figure 2-2 The ePLANET platform log in.....	12
Figure 2-3 The ePLANET observatory platform	13
Figure 2-4 UC1 ePLANET platform; how to add a new action from the SECAP	14
Figure 2-5 UC1 ePLANET platform; Action plan in Chanion	15
Figure 2-6 UC1 ePLANET platform; Evaluation of Chanion action adaptation plan	16
Figure 2-7 UC1 ePLANET platform; Ripoll adaptation plan summary	17
Figure 2-8 UC1 ePLANET platform; actions tab for Vilablareix (Girona Province)	18
Figure 2-9 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the sources.....	19
Figure 2-10 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the sources	20
Figure 2-11 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the applications ..	21
Figure 2-12 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the applications ..	22
Figure 2-13 UC2 ePLANET platform; Elements in the municipality of Karolinka	23
Figure 2-14 UC2 ePLANET platform: Energy consumption of Skolni Budova building in the Karolinka municipality	24
Figure 2-15 UC2 ePLANET platform: Actions tab of Regional building in Zlin Region	25
Figure 2-16 UC2 ePLANET platform; Elements in the municipality of Chanion	26
Figure 2-17 Screenshot UC3 - The GIS Crete.....	27
Figure 2-18 Linked data fields of the ePLANET.....	28
Figure 2-19 Daily Load Curves for one residential building in the municipality of Palafrugell. The first graph showcases January's electrical consumption and the second showcases August's electrical consumption	30
Figure 2-20 Screenshot UC4 LIDAR points with elevation for the Zlín region	31
Figure 3-1 Girona (Girona Province) workshop in May 2023.....	32
Figure 3-2 Arkalohori (Crete Island) workshop in June 2023	33
Figure 3-3 Usability test answers to which is the reason of using the platform	34
Figure 3-4 Usability test answers to how often de they use the platform or plan to use it	34
Figure 3-5 Usability test platform experience and interactions ratings	35
Figure 0-1 Som Comunitat Energetica Logo	39
Figure 0-2 Grid Singularity Logo.....	39
Figure 0-3 Project Sunroof Logo	40
Figure 0-4 AURORA - Smart Solar Power Logo	40
Figure 0-5 Roofpedia Logo	41

Figure 0-6 Tetraeder.solar Logo 41

Figure 0-7 KM0 Logo 41

Figure 0-8 Power Quartier Logo 42

Figure 0-9 SimStadt Logo 42

Figure 0-10 EnerMaps Logo 43

Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CIMNE	International Centre for Numerical Methods in Engineering
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
DdGi	Diputació de Girona
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EAZK	Energy Agency of the Zlín Region
EC	Energy Communities
EEM	Energy Efficiency Measure
ET	Energy Transition
EU	European Union
GHG	Green House Gasses
GIS	Geographic Information System
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MoA	Memorandum of Adhesion
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PV	Photovoltaics
RDFC	Regional Development Fund of Crete
SAM	System Advisor Model
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
UC	Use Case

1 Introduction

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action co-funded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims at deploying new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

One of the key actions to implement this digital framework is the development of a platform to digitise the energy transition measures and actions carried out by the participating municipalities and meet the specific needs identified in each of the three pilots. The result will be a multi-platform or federated platform.

During the execution of the project, there will be different versions of the platform as new modules and components are developed. Thus, three versions of this document will be presented, one per year in months 13, 24 and 36, summarising the platform's progress. This document is the second version detailing the platform's status after the second year.

2 ePLANET federated platform

The ePLANET platform is composed of different platforms, from architectures, either components or processes developed by CIMNE on existing platforms, or purpose-built applications to meet the needs identified in the three pilot sites in the region of Zlín, the province of Girona and the island of Crete.

These needs, previously identified in a survey addressed to the municipalities of the three pilots, are included in the work of WP2 and specifically in deliverable D2.3 Data fields for ET harmonisation. The final product is intended to be a federated ePLANET platform, a set of tools to help pilot and follower regions implement energy transition measures, making local energy policies and decisions based on evidence-based facts and figures.

Figure 2-1 The ePLANET federated platform

Different versions of the platform are anticipated during the project's progression, coinciding with the design of new modules and components. The evolution of the versions will be governed by the feedback provided by end users with the ultimate goal of achieving a platform that digitises energy transition measures and meets the specific needs of each of the three pilots.

For this reason, in M13, the first version of the document was delivered, detailing and summarising the platform's progress and status after the first year. By then, a prototype was developed to be used by early-adopter groups of pilot regions, taking as a starting point the architecture, components and process developed by CIMNE in existing platforms of previous

projects and initiatives focused on the improvement of energy management of PPAs (SHERPA, EDI-net, etc.).

In this updated version, adjustments have been incorporated into the initial platform prototype, influenced by suggestions and recommendations gathered from usability test surveys, as well as user feedback obtained during workshops for platform training and consultation. In addition, the ePLANET common data model has also been implemented. With all this, the result is the platform prepared to extend the services to any region of the EU.

Worth noting that an API has been developed to establish communication between the ePLANET platform with the CIMNE system, where the SECAPs and the consumption and emissions data provided by the pilots have been harmonised and stored.

2.1 Preliminary concepts

Before proceeding with the technical analysis of the platform for each Use Case (UC), some preliminary concepts of the UC1 and UC2 visualisation module and access to it will be detailed.

The most vital adaptation with no reference to the UC is the language adaptation made to improve the understanding of the platform concepts to the end users of each pilot region. Even though the platform was already available in Catalan, the national language of Girona province, it has been translated into Greek and Czech, the regional languages of Crete Island and Zlín region. EAZK (Energy Agency of the Zlín Region), the Czech pilot coordinator, have checked and corrected these translations to avoid misconceptions. Finally, considering that the platform can be used by any European municipality, like the follower regions, it has also been translated into English, as a common language for all these municipalities that could take advantage of the ePLANET project outcomes. The language must be selected before logging in since, once inside, there is no chance of modifying it.

Figure 2-2 The ePLANET platform log in

Currently, the platform has uploaded SECAPs (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan) data from 67 municipalities in the province of Girona and 16 municipalities on the island of Crete. Additionally, data from 1721 buildings on Crete Island and 377 buildings in the Zlín region have also been incorporated into the platform. It should be noted that the Zlín region not only has a project for each municipality where the building data has been reported (as in Crete); also, another project has been created that encompasses all regional buildings, including those that do not depend on the municipality itself but whose use depends on the regional administrative bodies.

Once the user has been identified on the platform, the first tab that appears is the Observatory panel. From this visualisation, it is possible to glimpse the indicators established in the platform on a map, e.g., the municipality's energy consumption, GHG emissions, etc. Furthermore, these indicators can be selected from just one to all the municipalities to compare the results. The municipalities can be comparted between them in this first visualisation panel. The municipal level complete panel is shown entering specifically to one municipality. These visualisations correspond to the UC1 and UC2 described in sections 2.2 and 2.3, respectively.

Figure 2-3 The ePLANET observatory platform

In the preceding Figure, it is evident that the municipalities have been depicted using distinct colours, adhering to the following set of guidelines:

- Municipalities exhibiting an average value that oscillates within the bounds of the entire region's median values shall be rendered in an orange hue.
- A municipality's average value, exceeding the regional average by 10% or more, shall be represented in red, signifying its need to enhance its consumption rates, emissions, or any other aspect under analysis.
- Conversely, a municipality's average value, falling 10% or more below the regional average, will be painted in green, indicating that the municipality is an example to follow.

For more details about each municipality, it is only necessary to select it, and the platform will redirect the user to it. A comprehensive platform analysis will be developed in the subsequent sections, providing detailed information on the UCs.

2.2 UC1 - Digitalisation of SECAPs drafting and monitoring process

The Use Case 1 (UC1) services are provided in the Girona and Crete pilots through the user interface of the SIE software tool. The tool feed by the ePLANET database through the harmonisation layer presents the SECAPs data.

In the case of the Crete Island pilot, as there is no availability to get the SECAPs template, the data is gathered from the Global Covenant of Mayors data collection made available by the JRC. Previously, all the actions were reported to the CoM platform, so all actions from that period are available through the JRC periodic report; however, with the new SECAPS form, are only reported the key actions to the CoM, therefore only these actions are available on the JRC data collection.

The screenshot shows the 'New measurement.' form in the ePLANET platform. The form includes the following fields and controls:

- Measurement title:** A text input field.
- Sector:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Select an option'.
- Climate risk:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Select an option'.
- Description:** A large text area for entering details.
- Responsible:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder 'Select a responsible person'.
- Total energy savings (kWh):** A text input field.
- Renewable energy production (kWh):** A text input field.
- Emissions avoided (TCO₂):** A text input field.
- Cost (€):** A text input field.
- Annual savings (€):** A text input field.
- Start date:** A dropdown menu showing '2018'.
- End date:** A dropdown menu showing '2018'.
- Execution status (%):** A progress bar with three segments: 'Not started' (green), 'In progress' (grey), and 'Completed' (grey).
- Buttons:** 'Return' and 'Save' buttons at the bottom right.

Figure 2-4 UC1 ePLANET platform; how to add a new action from the SECAP

The Girona province pilot data will be imported automatically through the standard SECAP template. SECAPS were renewed during autumn 2022 with figures from 2019. In the case of Girona province, to complement the data from the SECAP, the public buildings consumption is

obtained from the already existing energy management tools (like the one developed in the project by the UC2).

To be able to manage this data, the Memorandums of Adhesions (MoA) signed by each municipality are needed. In this pilot, MoAs incorporate permission to access the municipality platforms to gather this data. The MoA has been sent to 67 municipalities in the province of Girona, and all the municipalities have signed them, providing us access credentials to their energy management platform. During this year, it is also expected to get access to DATADIS, a platform that allows access to the data of all municipal electric suppliers regardless of the DSO or the management system.

All the actions from the action plans defined in the SECAPS and uploaded manually or automatically onto the ePLANET platform are summarised under the "Planning" tab. When accessing the tab, the first step is to select the type of actions we want to analyse, as they are categorised separately based on whether they are adaptation actions (anticipating the harmful effects of climate change and taking appropriate measures) or mitigation actions (making the effects of climate change less severe by reducing GHGs into the atmosphere). Once the desired action plan is selected, a summarised table containing all the actions entered into the platform will be presented. These actions can be edited with the purpose of updating their execution status.

CHANIA ACTION PLAN (MITIGATION) 2012-2030

	Measure	Intervention area	Start	Final	Responsible	Cost [€]	Energy savings [kWh]	Renewable production [kWh]	Execution status (%)
	test	Energy efficiency	2023	2024	Responsible	0,00	2,00	10,00	0
	Replace plants used in parks with other with less demand in water and more resistant in climate change	Others	2018	2023	Municipality	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
	Development of a Technological and Economic Research Study on the Application of Renewable Energy Sources in Municipal Buildings and Facilities	Others	2018	2018	Municipality	0,00	0,00	0,00	0
	Supply and installation of photovoltaic panels on the roof of the DEYAH office building	Others	2018	2018	DEYA Chania	0,00	0,00	0,00	0

Figure 2-5 UC1 ePLANET platform; Action plan in Chanion

To assess the implementation of the action plan and determine the current level of completion, it is possible to visualise the execution status of each action and the execution schedule. This allows for monitoring each action's progress and determining the completion percentage at any moment.

Plan summary

Figure 2-7 UC1 ePLANET platform; Ripoll adaptation plan summary

The "Actions" tab displays the processes and changes implemented to fulfil the proposed measures for each municipality.

The screenshot displays the 'Actions' tab in the ePLANET platform. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Accounting', 'Management', and 'Administration' menus. Below this, the 'Actions' section is visible, featuring a search bar with '1 Selected' and a date range of '01/01/2018 - 31/12/2022'. A table with columns for 'Action', 'Description', 'Use acting', 'Scope of action', 'Element', 'Date', and 'Investment (€)' is shown, but it is currently empty with the message 'No data to show'. Below the table, there are two summary boxes: 'No. of actions by scope (01/01/2018 - 31/12/2022)' and 'Investments in actions by scope (01/01/2018 - 31/12/2022)', both of which also display 'No data to show'.

Figure 2-8 UC1 ePLANET platform; actions tab for Vilablareix (Girona Province)

However, as shown in Figure 2-8, no record of actions can currently be found in the tab since the municipalities still need to store this information. From now on, thanks to the ePLANET platform, they can keep all this information in it.

For this UC1 in the platform, the Municipal Balance tab has also been created. Upon accessing it, the first step is to select the period in which the analysis is to be performed, and consequently, it will display the data for that period. Additionally, it allows the user to select the type of measure to be displayed (consumption or emissions) and the energy sources (electricity, fossil fuels, LPG, natural gas, or renewables).

Once the input data is chosen, the ePLANET platform plots the data based on the energy source or based on the application. If the visualisation is selected based on the energy source, all the consumptions or emissions will be disaggregated according to the energy source (Figure 2-9 and Figure 2-10). On the other hand, as can be seen in Figure 2-11 and Figure 2-12, if the visualisation is chosen based on applications, the consumption or emissions will be differentiated according to the sector in which the consumption occurs (transportation, industrial, residential, services, or municipality). Finally, highlight that all the information and graphs can be exported in many formats, such as PNG, JPG, PDF, SVG, and XLS.

Figure 2-9 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the sources

Distribution annual by sources (2015 - 2019)

Sources	2015		2016		2017		2018		2019	
	kWh	%								
Fuels	93.961.867	36,91	101.368.923	38,97	106.438.100	39,83	112.977.188	40,85	118.105.761	42,48
Electricity	94.785.042	37,24	92.561.412	35,59	93.888.413	35,13	94.957.284	34,33	85.936.988	30,91
Natural gas	62.260.484	24,46	62.425.704	24,00	63.345.630	23,70	65.599.040	23,72	71.474.432	25,71
LPG	3.528.642	1,39	3.734.901	1,44	3.583.235	1,34	3.054.241	1,10	2.484.880	0,89
Renewables	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
Fossil fuel	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
Total	254.536.035		260.090.940		267.255.378		276.587.753		278.002.061	

Figure 2-10 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the sources

Figure 2-11 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the applications

Distribution annual by applications (2015 - 2019)

Applications	2015		2016		2017		2018		2019	
	kWh	%								
Transport	82.214.656	32,30	92.115.946	35,42	97.413.657	36,45	103.813.591	37,53	109.962.231	39,55
Industrial	97.691.060	38,38	96.279.968	37,02	98.877.212	37,00	95.500.760	34,53	95.275.888	34,27
Residential	51.394.218	20,19	47.904.148	18,42	47.370.770	17,72	50.682.821	18,32	47.380.824	17,04
Services	23.236.101	9,13	23.790.878	9,15	23.593.739	8,83	26.590.581	9,61	25.383.118	9,13
City council	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00
Total	254.536.035		260.090.940		267.255.378		276.587.753		278.002.061	

[Export data to Excel](#)

Balance consumption invoiced annual by applications and sources (2019)

Figure 2-12 UC1 ePLANET platform; Municipal balance of Ripoll based on the applications

2.3 UC2 - Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock

The Use Case 2 (UC2) services are provided in the Zlín region and Crete Island pilots through the user interface of the SIE software tool. The tool feed by the ePLANET database through the harmonisation layer presents the public building stock analysis.

A new tab called "Elements" has been created on the platform to display and analyse all the data for this UC. When accessed, the first step is to select the analysis period for which we want the data. Once the selection is made, the platform will show the disaggregated consumption for each building according to the energy source (electricity, gas, etc.) and the percentage of consumption it represents compared to the total number of buildings in the municipality. Additionally, a map visually indicates the georeferenced location (longitude and latitude) of each building.

Figure 2-13 UC2 ePLANET platform; Elements in the municipality of Karolinka

The Elements tab (Figure 2-13) only illustrates a summary of all the information available in the municipality. For this reason, if we select one of the buildings (either from the table itself or the map), another tab will open, providing more detailed information about the building's characteristics and consumption. This tab has a pie chart showing the consumption percentages for each energy type, a table displaying monthly consumption details, and a bar graph illustrating the annual consumption trend (Figure 2-14).

Figure 2-14 UC2 ePLANET platform: Energy consumption of Školní Budova building in the Karolinka municipality

Additionally, about this specific use case, it is worth noting that within the "Actions" tab, the documentation of Energy Efficiency Measures (EEM) executed at the building level for the Zlín region has been incorporated. Conversely, it should be highlighted that no such corresponding record was available for the Crete Island pilot.

No. of actions by scope (01/01/2022 - 31/12/2022)

Figure 2-15 UC2 ePLANET platform: Actions tab of Regional building in Zlín Region

Finally, highlight that all the information and charts can be exported in many formats, such as PNG, JPG, PDF, SVG, and XLS.

All the Crete island uploaded buildings in the visualisation platform have the name of their municipality. Consequently, an exceptional identification method has been agreed with the pilot and implemented to establish clear distinctions between buildings. This method involves concatenating the building's name with its street and the building street number when available.

Figure 2-16 UC2 ePLANET platform; Elements in the municipality of Chania

2.4 UC3 - GEO-Tools for the promotion of energy communities

Use Case 3 (UC3) services are expected in the three pilots: Zlín region, Girona province and Crete island pilots. However, in Zlín Region the development of UC3 has not started yet. Each pilot site will have its user interface.

2.4.1 Crete island pilot

The user interfaces for the island of Crete will be performed through the provided platform “GIS Crete”, which will be fed with the processed data through the mapping, with the necessary data transformations, designed databases, and allocated in them to expose the renewable energy installations in the island.

Figure 2-17 Screenshot UC3 - The GIS Crete

CIMNE has worked on the preliminary data provided by pilot sites to develop the analytic modules for accepting their input in the harmonised data format of ePLANET.

Figure 2-18 Linked data fields of the ePLANET

2.4.2 Girona province pilot

Nowadays, in the province of Girona, many inhabitants are interested in promoting and implementing energy communities. In fact, the Girona provincial council is currently promoting a total of 120 energy communities. However, the process is prolonged since there is an administrative block on the implementation of these communities. That is why the paradigm has changed concerning the beginning of the project in which the need was a tool to promote energy communities. Now the prior need to develop this tool is to overcome this administrative hurdle.

For this reason, it was decided to modify the initial UC3 for this pilot and use the corresponding technical resources to study and connect to all the data sources used by the municipalities to develop their SECAP. In the development of the SECAPs the municipalities have to do the time-consuming task of collecting all the required data to report to the CoM. For this, the UC3 is reoriented to reinforce the UC1 and support the municipalities in this direction by performing a dynamic update, allowing dynamic control of the municipal energy transition.

The efforts undertaken in the development of the initial UC3, with the goal of developing a tool to enhance the establishment of energy communities, are detailed below.

2.4.2.1 Study of energy community's creation existing platforms

Several platforms and companies exist regarding the current development of Energy Communities and actions related to this, which either promote and help the creation of ECs, simulate them or monitor the energy usage across a given area.

Most presented platforms are tools to map solar PV potential, irradiation, or energy consumption, while some are open-source, making them extendable to other areas. The interesting feature is that part of them are combined with deep learning algorithms (such as CNN- ConvolutionalNeuralNetwork), Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) or Decision Support System (DSS), depending on the purpose. In most instances, the data is obtained from public

authorities. The ones that are GIS-based most frequently use ArcGIS - the web-based mapping software and interactive map builder.

Analysis has been conducted on a total of 23 distinct platforms, comprising 13 GIS-based systems and 10 tools designed to promote energy communities. The detailed platform analysis is provided in Annex 1. All the considered platforms and services have similar features to the upcoming ePLANET platform. It is important to analyse all the already existing solutions before developing a new idea.

The closest concept to the ePLANET one is the Som Comunitat Energetica service since it is also GIS-based, and it is possible to simulate a potential energy community by simply choosing the rooftops in the proximity of a 500-meter radius. However, contrary to the ePLANET project, it does not include real and detailed energy consumption data on a building level - the calculations are based only on the rooftop solar potential. This feature, coupled with geographical coordinates and PV solar potential for individual rooftops, makes the ePLANET GIS-based platform stand out from its competitors. With these characteristics, the potential creation of Energy Communities is more supported because it is based on real historical data, and therefore it is more reliable. The Som Comunitat Energetica idea is missing the support of the local authorities, and it does not involve municipalities in the creation of the ECs. In the case of the ePLANET project, it is crucial to use public buildings in the analysis and choose rooftops around with the most beneficial and varied load profiles in order to use as much generated electricity as possible.

2.4.2.2 Energy community's creation platforms development

In the Girona province case, they wanted a tool to create energy communities. However, according to Spanish regulation, the energy community must be within a radius of a certain distance from the generation. For this purpose, the electrical and gas consumptions are obtained from the distributor system operators and geolocalised. The electrical consumption is on a monthly basis, and through the DATADIS data, which presents the hourly postal code energy consumption, the hourly energy consumption of all the municipality buildings is estimated.

The estimation of each building's hourly electrical energy consumption is done for 6 municipalities.

Figure 2-19 Daily Load Curves for one residential building in the municipality of Palafrugell. The first graph showcases January's electrical consumption and the second showcases August's electrical consumption

2.5 UC4 - PV potential analysis for public buildings

The Use Case 4 (UC4) services are provided in the Zlín region pilot, consisting of identifying public buildings and analysing the impact of PV facilities on those rooftops.

The PV potential analysis is performed through GIS systems. To make it is used the geolocation of the public buildings provided in the UC2 with the LIDAR data from the scan of all the roofs from the Zlín Region. Moreover, to better identify the limits of the building, the Cadastral data is used to obtain the shape of the public buildings to analyse.

Once the building is identified, some algorithms are applied to determine the tilting of the roof from the LIDAR point cloud. Next, this data is used in the SAM (System Advisor Model) to get the roofs' potential PV production.

Figure 2-20 Screenshot UC4 LIDAR points with elevation for the Zlín region

3 Platform continuous engagement and improvements

To ensure that the pilot regions fully commit to the project and use the ePLANET platform, some workshops have been conducted focusing on its training and usage. The objective is to achieve a continuous enhancement of the platform. As part of this effort, the technicians attending the workshops have also participated in a platform usability survey. The feedback obtained from the technicians through the usability survey has provided diverse opinions, allowing for ongoing improvements to the platform.

3.1 Platform training

With the aim of training technicians in the pilot regions, informative workshops have been conducted in the pilot regions. These workshops have been designed to provide comprehensive knowledge and skills to the technicians, equipping them with the necessary tools to effectively carry out their tasks and contribute to the project's success. A team of experienced trainers and experts in the field has been assembled to ensure the effectiveness of the workshops. These trainers provided theoretical knowledge and facilitated practical exercises and simulations on the platform. The participants have been actively engaged through group discussions, allowing them to apply their newly acquired knowledge in real-world scenarios.

In Girona province, CIMNE and ICAEN held a face-to-face workshop on May 2nd 2023, where 12 technicians attended.

Figure 3-1 Girona (Girona Province) workshop in May 2023

In the case of the island of Crete, RDFC organised a series of 6 in-person workshops on June 2023 with the assistance of CIMNE and CRES enrolling municipalities across all the island.

Figure 3-2 Arkalohori (Crete Island) workshop in June 2023

Finally, workshops have yet to be held in the Zlín region. CIMNE has set a training session for EAZK project partners in September 2023, followed by their responsibility to lead the training in the Zlín region during October 2023.

3.2 Usability test survey results and conclusions

A usability test survey of the platform, as a follow-up to T3.3, has been designed to collect impressions and feedback from the users. The survey was sent to all the technicians and managers participating in the project and who will be using the ePLANET platform. All survey results can be found in Annex 2.

The survey consists of 15 questions of different types: Multiple choice, Rating scale and Open-ended questions, which are divided into three blocks:

- Identification: 2 questions for internal use in the project.
- General questions: 5 questions to understand how the user uses the platform.
- Specific questions: 8 questions to evaluate specific aspects of the platform; user interface and user experience, and suggestions for improvements.

Since not all pilots participate in all UCs, a common-to-specific questions approach analysis will be performed to evaluate results. Remark that Girona Province only has access to the part of the platform referring to UC1, Zlín Region to UC2 and the Island of Crete to both UCs. In addition, the Observatory part is enabled for the three pilot regions.

The usability test survey of the ePLANET platform was circulated in the three pilot sites and has collected 20 answers. Eight technicians from the Energy Transition Offices in the Girona region attended the workshop, so the total count of responses by the Catalan pilot was 8. Additionally, 10 municipal technicians on the Island of Crete responded to the survey. Finally, in the Zlín region, two responses were obtained, corresponding to the technicians of the EAZK

team. Those pre-established or multiple-option questions are analysed jointly for the three pilots.

Figure 3-3 Usability test answers to which is the reason of using the platform

From the upper graph, it is evident that the main reasons to use the ePLANET platform are concentrated on the same options, which correspond to the key features the platform is covering. The two answers with the lowest ratios are features not enabled in this platform version.

Figure 3-4 Usability test answers to how often de they use the platform or plan to use it

When asked about the platform's frequency of use, a wide variety of responses cover all cases. However, 35% responded that they use it occasionally, and the 30% uses on a weekly basis being this significant as the three pilots represent it. It is also remarkable that 2 members of the Girona pilot use it daily.

The following charts show the results of user experience and interactions with the platform by rating the questions from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very).

Figure 3-5 Usability test platform experience and interactions ratings

From these last graphs, it can be observed that in general, the vast majority of responses are rated as “3” and “4” by most respondents, with a very sharp trend from neutrality to positivity. This demonstrates, on the one hand, that the platform generally meets expectations. For instance, when asked about satisfaction, 55% rated as “4” and 45% as “3”. On the other hand, the results of the above questions show that there are no apparent weaknesses.

Finally, a summary of the main comments obtained from the open-ended questions is shown by each pilot in the following chapters.

3.2.1 The platform usability in Girona pilot

The statements of the survey circulated in Girona Region stand out a general satisfaction with the ePLANET platform among all the technicians; in fact, they all confirmed that it is a very intuitive platform and, thanks to it, it is easier to integrate the information and therefore, link the measures and monitor the actions of the SECAPs. In addition, given that the data visualisation is user-friendly, it allows the users to see the execution status of the SECAPs quickly and consequently make strategic decisions speedy. On the other hand, they also provided a range of suggestions and recommendations that, in their opinion, should be improved or changed. These are listed below and will be considered in the following platform updates.

- The province of Girona is distributed in 8 regional councils, and each technician is associated with one, so they showed interest in making a regional council aggregation.
- An action (Energy Efficiency measure) can be completed without the expected results; therefore, the technicians suggest applying a success rate to each action.
- Add as much historical data as possible to assess the evolution of consumption and emissions and make decisions based on it.
- The terms "measures" and "actions" are valid; however, it would be helpful if a small message displays that the measures are the actions of the SECAPs.
- On the observatory entrance map, it would be friendly to visualise more variables to compare the territory at the consumption level and in the progress of SECAPs measures.
- Allow an annual assessment of consumption according to the methodology applied to SECAPs.
- It requires considerable human effort to maintain the platform and, consequently, get benefit from it.
- The execution status of the actions is: not started, in progress and completed. The technicians suggest that in the status "in progress", it would be helpful to be able to set a percentage (ex: 30-50%) that they could modify based on the follow-up meetings they have with the municipality councils.

Finally, given the interest shown by all the technicians in persisting in using the platform once the project has ended, they were asked a maximum cost that they thought the platform could have for each municipality. The answers ranged between 200-500€/year for each municipality. They argued that the price should be lower than the SECAPs monitoring report and different for each municipality since not all have the same capacities or volume of actions.

3.2.2 The platform usability in Crete pilot

About Crete Island, the usability test survey of the ePLANET platform was circulated among the technicians from the municipalities who attended the workshops, both online and face-to-face. As already said, ten responses have been obtained.

Based on the survey findings, the Crete municipalities' technicians have reaffirmed the platform's user-friendly and intuitive interface for efficient information management. Furthermore, the technicians expressed their appreciation for the "observatory" functionality, which empowers them to oversee the progress of energy efficiency measures across different municipalities and facilitate comparisons.

Despite the positive feedback, the technicians identify areas for improvement within the platform. One notable issue is inaccurate data, where data of buildings and pumpings has been intermingled and categorised as buildings. Addressing this data accuracy concern is paramount to enhancing the platform's reliability.

Furthermore, the technicians recommend the inclusion of additional indicators, both quantitative and qualitative, such as energy payback period, CO2 payback time, profits, etc. These supplementary indicators would significantly contribute to a more comprehensive evaluation of investments and their efficiency and facilitate the presentation of a summarised analysis in the form of a report. They pointed out that this report should encompass environmental, financial, and energy-related indicators, allowing for a more holistic assessment. Lastly, the technicians suggest the inclusion of explicit instructions within the platform's menu.

Also, one technician pointed out that one of the sixteen municipalities of the pilot was misplaced in the Observatory map. The municipality of Apokoronou was misplaced in the Amari municipality area. This error has already been fixed in the platform.

In addition to their feedback on the ePLANET platform, they have also informed about HEDNO (Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator), the Greek Electricity Distribution Network Operator. They point out that integrating their data into the ePLANET platform could automate updating consumption information.

Finally, they were asked the maximum cost they believed the platform could have for each municipality. The responses ranged from €50-500/year for each municipality. They argued that some platforms are already being developed in the context of Smart Cities, which will integrate this data.

3.2.3 The platform usability in the Zlín region pilot

Lastly, the usability test survey of the ePLANET platform was circulated among the two technicians of EAZK who are collaborating with the development of the platform on the part of the Czech pilot.

The comments provided by the technicians from the Zlín region were based on the fact that even though the platform is an instant "one-stop shop" feature and allows uploading new data and comparing them to old ones, sometimes the platform is not intuitive as it might be.

Finally, regarding what price they think the municipalities would be willing to pay for the ePLANET platform, both responded that EAZK is a non-profit organisation supported by the Zlín Region and EU funds, and the services that they provide to municipalities are free of charge; for this reason, they believe that municipalities would not be willing to commit to paying regular fees for the platform.

4 Conclusions

The main goal of this document is to provide the status of the development of the ePLANET platform after the second year. It will be followed by a third version at the end of the project, which will outline the final platform developed during the project with all the tools and features enabled.

This second version presents the platform's visualisations for use cases 1 and 2 up to date. These visualisations also showcase the pilots' datasets and the translation into the local languages. Finally, the work done so far is outlined for use cases 3 and 4, which are more specific for each pilot region. It includes the processing and mapping of the data provided to obtain a robust and harmonised database that can be easily integrated with data from other regions out of the pilots.

In addition, the results of the usability testing survey performed to 20 technicians of the pilot regions are presented. It demonstrates that the platform generally meets the expectations in the three pilots with an overall positivity of answers in terms of navigation, understandability of the information, usefulness, operability and overall satisfaction. It is also remarkable that there are no apparent weaknesses in general. However, there are suggestions for improvement from specific individuals that would be studied individually to assess the possibility of implementation. For instance, the presence of inaccurate data mixing buildings and pumping stations data in the Crete pilot version is crucial to resolve in order to make it a handy tool.

Annex 1 Energy Communities promotion platforms state of the art

GIS-Platforms

1- Som Comunitat Energetica

Developed in the Institute for Energy Research of Catalonia (IREC) in Spain. The main objective is to boost the energy transition of the building stock towards decarbonisation by promoting the creation of energy communities from an inclusive and supportive perspective. It is an interactive map based on the satellite picture, which includes an algorithm for recognising potential energy communities. The main feature is the information about the solar radiation of each rooftop in the neighbourhood and the ability to simulate the creation of EC to discover energy and economic savings.

Figure 0-1 Som Comunitat Energetica Logo¹

2- Grid Singularity

Energy exchange software development company that simulates and operates interconnected grid-aware energy marketplaces. Grid Singularity facilitates market participation by connecting aggregators and grid operators through an application interface. Grid Singularity Exchange provides the software tools, enabling prosumers and consumers organised in energy communities, with the support of local aggregators, to simulate and implement peer-to-peer and community energy trading through the creation of active local energy markets. It is a "digital twin" representation of physical energy systems and energy markets.

Figure 0-2 Grid Singularity Logo²

¹ Som Comunitat Energetica, <https://somcomunitatenergetica.cat>, 2022

² Grid Singularity, <https://gridsingularity.com>, 2022

3- Project Sunroof

Developed by the collaboration between Google, E.ON, and Tetraeder.solar, a solar potential map based on Google Maps and machine learning processes, which allows the design of a future photovoltaic installation and expected reduction of the electricity bill. It considers shadows, all possible sun positions, historical clouds, and temperature patterns.

Figure 0-3 Project Sunroof Logo³

4- AURORA - Smart Solar Power

A platform that creates an entire engineering design and sales proposal with just an electric bill and an address after the selection of a particular rooftop. It uses LiDAR-assisted modelling and conducts shading analysis. After this process, it is able to calculate the price and simulate the energy production of the potential installation. It operates in the USA.

Figure 0-4 AURORA - Smart Solar Power Logo⁴

5- Roofpedia

Automatic mapping of green and solar roofs for an open roofscape registry and evaluation of urban sustainability. It combines deep-learning and geospatial techniques demonstrating the feasibility of an automated methodology that successfully generalises across cities with an accuracy detecting sustainable roofs of up to 100% in some cities. Furthermore, the method identifies both green and solar roofs, which adds another dimension to understanding the sustainability of the roofscape across cities. The model is created with international scalability in mind and can be used in multiple cities worldwide with different urban morphology and building typology.

³ Project Sunroof, <https://sunroof.withgoogle.com>, 2022

⁴ AURORA - Smart Solar Power, <https://aurorasolar.com>, 2022

Figure 0-5 Roofpedia Logo⁵

Tools for the municipalities for Energy Communities creation

Several companies provide a variety of tools that helps municipalities or citizens implement the Energy Communities concept. From just providing consultancy services through sharing relevant consumption or potential solar generation data to platforms through which it is possible to sell the excess electricity. Below a few of them are explained.

1- Tetraeder.solar

Big data for sales and power grid planning. The company helps with utilising vast amounts of data, such as a solar potential analysis of entire areas or even countries. The focus is on the development of forecasting and planning tools in the field of renewable energies, especially in the fields of photovoltaics, solar thermal energy and the use of energy storage, as well as the expansion of the PV and charging infrastructure. The services are mainly used by municipalities and public utilities/energy supply companies to support public relations and sales.

Figure 0-6 Tetraeder.solar Logo⁶

2- KMO

The company promotes, designs, implements and manages the Energy Communities, accompanying town councils and citizens throughout the energy transition process, empowering them and involving them in a new way of doing things. One of the goals is to implement 1GW of decentralised renewable energy in Catalonia, which is equivalent to a nuclear power plant. The generation plants that the company supports have citizen financing since the energy transition must have its engine in a social transformation. This allows citizens to have electricity generation ownership and move from a centralised system in the hands of large institutions to a decentralised citizen-based system.

Figure 0-7 KMO Logo⁷

⁵ Roofpedia, <https://ual.sg/project/roofpedia>, 2022

⁶ Tetraeder.solar, https://solar:tetraeder.com/de_v2, 2022

⁷ KMO Energy, <https://kmo.energy/en>, 2022

3- Power Quartier

The app accompanies households and businesses in the energy transition, providing insights into their consumption and showing them how photovoltaics reduce energy bills. The flagship service is a “Neighborhood Power” exchange, allowing an electricity-producing household to sell any surpluses to surrounding households. Both buyers and sellers participate in the local energy community via the PowerQuartier app, which shows energy data and generation sources. For example, on sunny days, users can see that the local photovoltaic system covers the whole community’s electricity demand. On rainy days, you see how much electricity the regional energy supplier is delivering to the community. In addition, the app supports municipalities in turning their political ambitions regarding the energy transition into reality and showing to the population possible courses of action.

PowerQuartier

Figure 0-8 Power Quartier Logo⁸

4- SimStadt

The aim is to provide a simulation environment that couples building requirement analyses with decentralised renewable feed-in via grid simulations, thus enabling scenarios for load management, storage dimensioning, and demand developments to be calculated. In the current stage of expansion, SimStadt can use data from a real urban development situation or a planning status for energy analyses of buildings, urban districts, entire cities and even regions. The application scenarios range from the high-resolution simulations of the building heating requirement to potential studies for photovoltaics to the simulation of building renovation and renewable energy supply scenarios.

Figure 0-9 SimStadt Logo⁹

⁸ KMO Energy, <https://km0.energy/en>, 2022

⁹ SimStadt, <https://www.hft-stuttgart.de/forschung/projekte/abgeschlossen/simstadt>, 2022

5- EnerMaps

It is a European project that was also involved in the H2020 projects, which provides an open data management tool that improves data management and accessibility in the field of the renewable energy industry. It aims to collect centralised energy data in a common platform with long-term support.

Figure 0-10 EnerMaps Logo¹⁰

¹⁰ EnerMaps, <https://enermaps.eu/news/enermaps-project-a-new-openenergy-data-tool-to-accelerate-the-energy-transition>, 2022

Annex 2 Usability testing survey

The usability survey was composed of 15 questions and translated into the local languages of the three pilot regions so that they could be answered directly by the technicians using the platform, with the exception of the Zlín pilot where the technicians are the same as the project participants, and were provided in English.

The following table includes the links to the survey for each pilot.

Pilot site	Language	Link to survey
Girona	Catalan	Usability testing survey - Girona pilot
Crete	Greek	Usability testing survey - Crete pilot
Zlín region	English	Usability testing survey - Zlín pilot

The questions and multiple choice answers were the same for all three pilots except for question 2, where the answers were adapted to the geographical area of each pilot. An example of the survey format is shown below.

Usability survey of the ePLANET platform

The following survey within the framework of the [ePLANET project](#) aims to detect potential improvements and new functionalities in order to make the Energy Information System platform more useful for the development of the project's services.

Number of questions: 15

Time to answer: 5 to 7 minutes

IDENTIFICATION

This information will only be used for internal management purposes of the ePLANET project.

1. Your name

2. What area of influence does your office cover? *

- Zlín Region
- Girona province
- Crete
- None of the above

GENERAL QUESTIONS

It allows us to understand what use you give to the ePLANET platform.

3. How often do you use the platform or plan to use it (given that you have recently received access)?

*

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Occasionally
- I have only accessed it once
- None of the above

4. Which of the following options are the main reasons for using it? *

- Monitoring energy efficiency measures
- Introducing new energy efficiency measures
- Calculating the impact of the energy efficiency measures
- Monitoring energy savings
- Monitoring energy consumption
- Draw conclusions to help in decision-making on energy efficiency measures that are more cost-effective?
- Optimise contracts and tariffs
- Manage the portfolio of buildings, municipalities or Energy Transition plans
- Drawing up monitoring reports of the Energy Transition plans
- Municipal energy planning monitoring tool
- Review energy bills and consumption
- None of the above

5. What do you think the maximum annual cost of the platform per municipality could be?

*

6. What do you like most about the platform? *

7. What do you like least about the platform? *

SPECIFIC QUESTIONS

Evaluate the following aspects of the platform on a scale of 1 to 5

8. How easy is it to navigate to find what you need? *

Slighty

Very

9. How clear and understandable is the information shown in the platform?

*

Slighty

Very

10. How useful are the features and functionalities of the platform for your needs?

*

Slighty

Very

11. To what extent does the information displayed on the platform help you to solve your day-to-day job issues?

*

Slighty

Very

12. How fast and user-friendly is the platform? *

<input type="radio"/>				
1	2	3	4	5
Slightly		Very		

13. How satisfied are you with the platform in general? *

<input type="radio"/>				
1	2	3	4	5
Slightly		Very		

14. Do you have any suggestions or recommendations to improve the platform?
*

15. Is there anything else you would like to share with us about your experience with the platform?
*

The [ePLANET project](#) is funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union under number GA 101032450.

SEND

